

International Seminar
Advances In Food Bio-Preservation
2-4 October 2022

International Seminar

Advances In Food Bio-Preservation, ISAFP, 2022

Tunis Science City, Tunisia, 2nd -4th, October 2022

Pre-Seminar Booklet, version 28/09/2022

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1. PREFACE

ARTISANEFOOD-2019-2023 project is a PRIMA-funded project aiming to develop simple, efficient and /or innovative bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, targeting the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in artisanal fermented foods with meat or dairy origin.

The International Seminar “Advances in Food Bio-preservation, ISAFBP 2022” is organized in the framework of ArtiSaneFood project. It offers the opportunity for researchers and PhD students to present their research results dealing with the application of natural food preservatives and biocontrol interventions of food (using natural plant extracts and/or lactic acid bacteria, LAB). Multifunctional properties (*in vitro* and *in vivo* assays) of biomolecules recovered from agro-industrial waste and those of LAB were also underlined through a special communication session. Three-minute E-Poster pitches session will be organized for selected posters. ISAFBP 2022 is also an opportunity to attend a fully practical workshop dealing with classic and dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology. The workshop features prominent experts in the field: Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron & Vasco Cadavez, from the Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza, Portugal.

We are grateful to all our colleagues from LR- Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules (ISBST, UMA), LR Livestock and Wildlife IRA Mednine (UG), LR, PATIO (INAT, UCAR), Post-Doc and PhD students for their valuable collaboration. Many thanks to Prof. ElHatmi H, Prof. Hammadi M, Prof. Khorchani, T and Prof. Ben Chaoucha Chekir, R for helping with organization ISAFBP 2022 and making it an interesting event for sharing valuable scientific results between researchers. Many thanks to Dr. Malek BenZid for significant contribution to seminar preparation since June 2022, to Dr. M’hiri Nouha and Prof. Maha Benlarbi for contribution to English reviewing of the booklet.

A special thank to Prof. Fethi Zagrouba (PDG, Tunis Science City, TSC, Tunisia) and all the team of CST for their availability, collaboration and for offering us a guided visits to TSC and to the Planetarium.

The final seminar of ARTISANEFOOD is programmed in May 2023 at The last seminar is to be held in the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança and will be another opportunity to meet in-person with all project partners. You can continue to follow ARTISANEFOOD project via the following links:

<http://ipb.pt/artisanefood/>; <https://facebook.com/artisanefood>.

On behalf of steering and organizing committees, Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua,

Artisanefood Project Lead for Tunisian Team

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2. PROJECT PRESENTATION

ARTISANEFOOD PROJECT: to increase food safety in artisanal fermented milk and dried meat and sausage

Title: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

Acronym: ARTISANEFOOD

Budget: 1.583708 €

Period: 36 months (to be achieved May 2023)

Call: PRIMA-S2-2018-PIC2019

Number: PRIMA/0001/2018

AIMS

The main object of this project is to develop efficient bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, aiming to the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in 15 artisanal fermented foods of meat or dairy origin produced in Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, Greece, Morocco and Tunisia.

It consists of an integrated risk-based approach sustained by the concepts of:

- (i) extensive tracking surveys in the artisanal food chains, in order to identify origin, routes of contamination, risk factors favouring pathogens' survival, and technological causes for lack of homogeneity in the quality/safety of end-products;
- (ii) biopreservation, whereby functional starter cultures and natural extracts will be assessed as extra hurdles to ensure safety and extend shelf-life;
- (iii) fate studies of pathogens, predictive dynamic modelling,
- (iv) risk process modelling, for the delineation of the most effective biointerventions, optimisation of process variables and norms/standards, and design of quality monitoring tools.

14h30-18h30	Classical versus dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
4th October 2022		
8h00-9h30	O2. Omnibus and microbial competition models – Theory (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron
9h30-10h00	Q/R Session Poster Pitches Session 2: E-Poster 14 to E-Poster 29	
10h00-10h30	Coffee Break	
LACTIC ACID BACTERIA & FOOD BIOPRESERVATION MODERATORS: PROF. HAMMADI, M PROF. KORCHANI T.		
10h30-10h40	O14. Characterization of traditional Tunisian arid zone fermented goat milk, Rayeb, using <i>Enterococcus faecium</i> isolated from dromedary-fermented milk	Khaoula Belguith
10h40-10h50	O15. Photosensitization effect of thyme essential oil for controlling plant pathogen <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> and <i>Alternaria alternata</i> in postharvest tomatoes	Dhekraa Trabelsi
10h50-11h00	O16. Effect of enzymatic hydrolysis on antioxidant activities of milk whey proteins from five different species	Meriem Ben Yagoub
11h10-11h20	O17. Camel milk casein as a potent source of natural antioxidant peptides	Zeineb Jrad
11h20-11h30	O18. Camel skim milk fermented by newly isolated autochthonous probiotic <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> : Quality characteristics and anti-obesity properties	Oufa Oussaief
11h30-11h40	O19. Anti-tumoral activity of <i>Allium roseum</i> compounds on Breast cancer cells MCF7 and MDA-MB231	Yosr Haffani
11h40-11h50	O20. How does dietary pomegranate peels incorporated in concentrate pellets affect lambs' meat quality and shelf life?	Hadhami Hajji
11h50-12h00	O21. Biological control methods against ochratoxin A-producing fungi isolated from grapes	Islem Dammak
12h00-12h15	Q/R Session	
12h15-13h15	Omnibus and microbial competition models – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
13h15-14h00	Lunch	
SPECIAL SESSION: Multi-functional biomolecules from agro-industrial waste: food bio-preservatives, antioxidants, <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> antidiabetic and anti-tumoral properties		
MODERATORS: PROF. HANEN NAJAA , PROF ESSID I, PROF. SIHEM BELLAGHA		
14h05-14h20	O22. Effects of antioxidant biomolecules extracted from agro-industrial byproducts on the prevention of diabetes and diabetic Retinopathy in Tunisian <i>Psammomys obesus</i> model (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Prof. Rafika Ben Chaouacha-Chekir
14h20-14h30	O23. Anti -diabetic activity of camel milk; findings in pancreatic beta cells	Amel Sboui
14h30-14h40	O24. Effects of olive mill wastewater compound on retinal function and astroglial glutamate metabolic networks in Diabetic	Oumaima Achour

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	Retinopathy <i>Psammomys obesus</i>	
14h40-14h50	O25. Effect of a biomolecule extracted from brown algae on molecular and cellular alterations in diabetic <i>Psammomys obesus</i> at the retinal and systemic level	Oumayma Hammami
14h50-15h00	O26. Evaluation of anti-hyperlipidemic effect and antioxidant activities of carotenoids extracted from halophilic <i>Archaea</i> – Case study of hyperlipidemic mice	Sana Ben Hamad Bouhamed
15h00-15h30	<p style="text-align: center;">Q/R Session</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Winner announcement for Poster Pitches Session , Round table discussion & Miscellaneous session</p>	
15h30-17h00	Guided visit to Tunis Science City of and to the Planetarium	Interested participants

Abstract N°: 9 (O9)

Thermal resistant parameters of *Salmonella Typhimurium* in alheira sausage batter

Sara Coelho-Fernandes^{1,2}, Vasco Cadavez^{1,2} and Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1,2*}

¹Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal; ²Laboratório para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: ubarron@ipb.pt

Previous studies have highlighted the need to implement better microbiological control and process standardization during the production of alheiras sausages, in particular during the stage of heat treatment. Alheira is a non-ready-to-eat sausage from Northern Portugal, which although at low prevalence, has shown survivability of *Salmonella* spp. throughout maturation. The objective of this work was to characterize the heat resistance of *Salmonella Typhimurium* (ST) in alheira sausage batter.

Two batches of alheira batter were obtained from a producer and inoculated with a ST overnight culture to reach ~ 7.0 log CFU/g. Bags containing well-spread 10-g alheira batter were submitted in duplicate to temperatures of 63°, 60°, 57° and 54 °C in an immersion bath, and sampled at 6 different time points. The quantification of ST on XLD plates was performed within two hours of the experiment.

A log-linear primary model fitted to each of the inactivation curves estimated the death rates of ST in alheira batter to be 0.038 (SE=0.008), 0.126 (SE=0.003), 0.273 (SE=0.063) and 2.872 (SE=0.763) log CFU/min at 54 °, 57 °, 60 ° and 63 °C, respectively, with coefficients of determination ranging between 0.914 and 0.987. Through a Bigelow model, the D-value (time needed to reduce ST in 1 log) was modelled as a function of temperature, resulting in a log D* of 2.302 (SE=0.304), corresponding to 200 minutes at 50 °C to reduce ST in 1 log, and a z-value of 5.016 (SE=0.839) °C. This model enables the prediction of D values and lethality times at other temperatures. For instance, to reach the 7.0 log reduction lethality of *Salmonella* spp. sought in sausages, the center of the alheiras should be kept for 9.0 seconds at 70 °C.

This study characterized for the first time the thermal kinetic parameters of a traditional Portuguese sausage and will be useful to producers for designing and controlling their thermal processes during alheira manufacture.

Key words: Foodborne pathogens; predictive microbiology; modelling; artisanal product; D value.

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